

UNIVERSITY OF COPENHAGEN

BACHELOR THESIS

**Studies of Dynamin 2 in
Megakaryocytes**

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Preamble

The present thesis is based on experiments conducted at Division of Translational Medicine, Brigham & Women's Hospital, Harvard Medical School in Boston. The experiments were designed by associate biologist Hervé Falet and conducted under supervision of postdoc Markus Bender. The thesis was written under supervision of professor Niels Borregaard, University of Copenhagen.

The thesis has the following structure. The *introduction* includes an account of relevant background knowledge, including an experimental motivation, a brief description of molecular structures and mechanisms central to the experiments and a presentation of the hypothesis. *Materials and methods* presents a description of the experiments conducted - a methodological triad comprising mutagenesis, retroviral production and viral transfection. The *result section* presents sequencing results following mutagenesis and two sets of pictures, one of retroviral production and one of viral transfection. The *discussion* includes a critical evaluation of the data and the experimental setup.

Resumé

Formålet med nærværende opgave var at undersøge dynamin 2's betydning for dannelse og funktion af blodplader. Konditioneret knockout af dynamin 2 i megakaryocytter hos mus er årsag til thrombocytopeni med macro-thrombocytter, splenomegali og megakaryocyt hyperplasi. I mennesker er mutationer i genet der koder for dynamin 2 årsag til Charcot-Marie Tooth sygdom. Med henblik på at undersøge funktionen af dynamin 2 i megakaryocytter, blev en række forsøg udført. Disse talte tre, nemlig mutagenese, retroviral produktion og retroviral transfektion. Det eksperimentelle mål var (i) at lokalisere dynamin 2 i megakaryocytter og (ii) at revertere blodpladedefekten i knockout mus ved at transfektere dynamin 2 ind i megakaryocytter fra disse. Da der ikke er antistoffer tilgængelige mod dynamin 2 blev lokalisationen forsøgt gennemført ved at undersøge lokalisationen af et fusionsprotein bestående af dynamin 2 og et fluorescerende protein. Dog lykkedes det hverken at lokalisere dynamin 2, eller at opnå tilstrækkelig transfektionseffektivitet af dynamin 2 i megakaryocytter, hvorfor spørgsmålet fortsat er ubesvaret.

I forlængelse af de eksperimentelle resultater følger en evaluering af eksperimenterne. Der konkluderes, at resultaterne var inkonklusive grundet begrænset erfaring og tid. Dermed er projektets egentlige konklusion ikke af videnskabelig karakter, men består i et erhvervet kompetencesæt. Herved forstås, at jeg i forbindelse med udarbejdelsen af opgaven har oparbejdet en beskedent laboratorieerfaring. Ydermere er jeg blevet bekendt med anvendelsen af den bibliografiske database Pubmed i forbindelse med at indhente og selektere videnskabelig information.

Abstract

The aim of the present thesis was to obtain an in-depth description of the role of dynamin 2 in platelet formation and activation of platelets. In mice, dynamin 2 knockout in the megakaryocyte lineage causes thrombocytopenia with macro-thrombocytes, splenomegaly and megakaryocyte hyperplasia. In humans, Charcot-Marie-Tooth disease is caused by dynamin 2 mutations. On that account, a series of experiments were designed to study megakaryocytes from dynamin 2 knockout mice. The experiments included mutagenesis, retroviral production and viral infection. The aim was to (i) locate dynamin 2 in megakaryocytes and (ii) rescue platelet deficiency in knockout megakaryocytes by transfecting dynamin 2 into the megakaryocytes. Since there is no antibody against dynamin 2, a fusion protein comprising of dynamin 2 and a fluorescent protein was constructed. Theoretically, fluorescence should then be used to locate dynamin 2. However, locating dynamin 2 failed. Consequently, the aim remains open to examination.

Subsequent to a presentation of the experimental results, the thesis comments on the experimental results and evaluates the experimental setup. It concludes that the results were inconclusive due to limited expertise and time. Hence, the main conclusion is not strictly scientific. Rather, it consists in the fact, that I gained modest laboratory experience in collecting data. Further, I became familiar with the bibliographic database Pubmed and learned how to use the tool in means of finding and selecting information.

Table of Contents

INTRODUCTION	2
EXPERIMENTAL MOTIVATION	2
THEORETICAL COMPONENTS	3
DYNAMIN	3
THROMBOPOIESIS	5
CHARCOT-MARIE-TOOTH DISEASE	6
EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH	7
EXPERIMENTAL MODEL	7
HYPOTHESIS	8
EXPERIMENTAL OBJECT	9
MATERIALS AND METHODS	9
PLASMID CONSTRUCT	9
MUTAGENESIS	9
DNA PURIFICATION	10
RETROVIRAL PRODUCTION	11
MEGAKARYOCYTE TREATMENT	12
ISOLATION	12
TRANSFECTION	12
METHODOLOGICAL ACHIEVEMENTS	12
RESULTS	13
MUTAGENESIS	13
RETROVIRAL PRODUCTION	14
MEGAKARYOCYTE TRANSFECTION	15
DISCUSSION	16
DESCRIPTIVE SUMMARY	16
EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION	17
EXPERIMENTAL LIMITS	17
CONCLUSION	18
REFERENCES	19

Introduction

Experimental Motivation

Platelets, the smallest member of the blood corpuscle, are unique in two aspects. Structurally, they are anucleate. Functionally, they are the cells regulating hemostasis. These structural and functional characteristics make them a prevalent object of scientific investigations(1).

In 1882 Giulio Bizzozero, the man who came to be known as the discoverer of platelets, described the existence of ‘constant blood particles, differing from red and white blood cells (...)’(2). Ever since, platelets have been studied intensely resulting in a deeper cellular understanding, which has formed the basis for various treatment regimes. In spite of many pharmacological contributions already, the field is still evolving(3). Despite subject of scientific investigation for centuries, much remains to be revealed about the mechanisms underlying normal platelet function. In particular the description of platelet formation and activation continually generates more questions than answers(1). With that in mind, a series of experiments were designed to study functional aspects of thrombopoiesis, the formation of platelets. The study included patients suffering from Charcot-Marie Tooth disease and a conditional dynamin 2 knockout mice. Charcot-Marie Tooth disease is an autosomal dominant neuromuscular disorder, which is caused by mutations in *DNM2*, the gene coding for dynamin 2. Specific *DMN2* mutations lead to thrombocytopenia in Charcot-Marie Tooth disease patients(4) and the conditional megakaryocyte lineage specific dynamin 2 knockout mice suffer from thrombocytopenia (unpublished data, Falet, H.). Hence, Charcot-Marie Tooth patients and conditional dynamin 2 knockout mice share affection site and their phenotypes overlap. Combined, these two features are the rational behind studying them jointly.

Figure 1 Experimental origin

In summary, an in-depth description of thrombopoiesis is the incentive behind the experiments that the present thesis presents. The hypothesis is that dynamin 2 is responsible for the fragmentation of platelets from their precursors and thereby the platelet synthesis. The hypothesis is grounded in two features. One is a clinical observation and one is theoretical hook derived from well-studied functions of dynamin isoforms elsewhere in the organism. The clinical observation is that Charcot-Marie Tooth disease is caused by *DNM2* mutations and that they suffer from thrombocytopenia(4). The theoretical hook is that the prime functions of

dynamins are obtained through interaction with the plasma membrane(5).

Three methods constitute the experimental approach. One is mutagenesis, one is retroviral production and one is retroviral transfection as presented in figure 2. The experimental subjects comprise a plasmid construct and megakaryocytes isolated from mouse embryos. The plasmid was constructed in such a way that dynamin 2 is fused with Dendra2. Dendra2 is a fluorescent protein, which has been modified from Dendra, a fluorescent protein derived from octocoral *Dendronephthya* sp(6, 7).

The mutagenesis was performed to acquire the correct DNA sequence in the plasmid used for transfection. Retroviral production was performed to allow transfection of the plasmid into the megakaryocytes. Finally, retroviral transfection was performed to induce the expression of Dendra2-dynamin 2 in megakaryocytes, and thus *locate* dynamin 2.

Figure 2 Experimental flowchart

Theoretical Components

Dynamins

Dynamins are large GTPases involved in a wide range of cellular functions, including membrane remodeling, endocytosis, intracellular trafficking and interaction with the actin and microtubule cytoskeletal networks. The mammalian genome encodes three dynamin isoforms. They share characteristics, in that they have GTPase activity, have affinity for various intracellular proteins, ability to oligomerize and are capable of binding lipid. Together, these characteristics enable dynamins to induce conformational changes, interact with a variety of other proteins and induce structural changes in the cellular membranes, resulting in membrane scission(5).

Initially, dynamin was identified as a protein associated with microtubules (8). Subsequently, various dynamin isoforms have been identified. Dynamin 1 is expressed mainly in neurons(9), dynamin 2 is ubiquitously expressed(10, 11) and dynamin 3 was originally purified from testis(12).

Figure 3 Three-dimensional structure of dynamin, PH: pleckstrin homology, GED: GTPase effector domain, PRD: proline rich domain(13)

Five domains make up the primary structure of a dynamin monomer, as illustrated in figure 3. The G domain, located at the very amino-terminus, is the site of GTPase activity. The middle domain and GTPase effector domain facilitate dimerization of dynamin(14). The pleckstrin homology domain is capable of binding to negatively charged membrane bound phospholipids, preferentially phosphatidylinositol-4,5-bisphosphate. The binding of the pleckstrin homology domain enhances GTPase activity(15). The carboxy-terminus part of the stalk, also termed GTPase effector domain, is functionally associated with the G domain as well and regulates the GTPase activity. Hence, it drives the dynamics of dynamin(16). The proline rich domain is capable of binding to various intracellular proteins. The interaction between dynamin and other intracellular proteins is involved in guiding dynamin molecules to the plasma membrane (17, 18). Further, the proline rich domain has various phosphorylation sites. Thus, it serves as a covalent modification site and facilitates the interaction between dynamin and a variety of other intracellular proteins(18).

A three-dimensional reconstruction of dynamin implies a 'T' shape characterized by three densities. They have been termed head, stalk and foot. Figure 3 presents the relationship between the primary structure and the three-dimensional structure of dynamin. The GTPase domain forms the head, the middle domain and GED form the stalk and the PH domain forms the foot(13).

The function of dynamin has been described in terms of a corkscrew model. According to the corkscrew model, dynamin function results from a conformational change in the head and stalk that collectively generates a twisting motion extending from the dynamin assembly. It has been assumed that the twisting motion is the sum of two forces. One results from a force parallel with the plasma membrane and one causes a force orthogonal to the plasma membrane (19, 20).

Figure 4 Structural and functional overview of DNAM(21)

Thrombopoiesis

Thrombopoiesis, the formation of blood platelets, takes place in the bone marrow. It is a highly regulated process and is essential for hemostasis. In humans, the daily platelet production amounts to approximately 1×10^{11} , and the circulatory life span is roughly 10 days(22).

Megakaryocytes are the myeloid cells that give rise to platelets(23) following a maturation process that temporally ranges from 4 to 7 days, originating at the megakaryoblast and ultimately leading to the formation of megakaryocytes(24). Megakaryocytes send long protrusions from the sinusoids of the bone marrow to the circulation, where these protrusions also called *pro-platelets* undergo fragmentation to form platelets. It has been estimated that one megakaryocyte gives rise to 1000 to 3000 platelets(22). Pro-platelets contain a characteristic distribution of microtubulin suggesting that it is involved in the fragmentation of platelets(25).

Figure 5 Pro-platelet formation in vitro (24)

Thrombopoiesis has certain unique characteristics. First, early in development the megakaryoblasts express a unique selection of surface molecules, including the integrin $\alpha_{IIb}\beta_3$ and the glycoprotein Ib-IX complex(26). The surface molecules function as receptors for fibrinogen and von Willebrand factor, respectively and occupy a key role in platelet activation and subsequent aggregation(27). Second, thrombopoiesis involves endomitosis, i.e. cell-division without physical separation of the daughter cells, resulting in polyploid, multinucleated cells(28). Third, thrombopoiesis involves extensive membrane rearrangement leading to the formation of a diverse set of intracellular compartments. These include, the demarcation membrane system and α -granules. The morphology of the demarcation membrane system is similar to the plasma membrane and is in open communication with the extracellular space. The current theory is that the demarcation membrane system is the structural basis for formation of pro-platelets(29). The α -granules are critical to normal platelet function, since they contain bioactive substances such as fibrinogen, platelet factor-4, von Willibrand factor, platelet derived growth factor and platelet receptors that mediate platelet rolling(30).

Charcot-Marie-Tooth Disease

In humans, mutations in *DNM2* cause Charcot-Marie Tooth disease, which is a neuromuscular disorder characterized by distal weakness and wasting of the limbs(4). Figure 6 summarizes the mutation sites in the dynamin 2 transcript that cause Charcot-Marie Tooth disease(31).

Figure 6 Charcot-Marie Tooth disease mutation sites in dynamin 2; Red circles mark location of mutation (Falet, H. adapted from(31))

One position, lysine 562, is central to the present investigation. Two mutations affecting the position have been associated with thrombocytopenia in Charcot-Marie-Tooth patients. One mutation results from a substitution of lysine for glutamic acid. The other mutation results from a deletion of lysine in position 562(4).

Figure 7 PH domain of dynamin 2, constructed from (32)

Figure 7 illustrates the pleckstrin homology domain of dynamin 2 comprising of one α -helix and seven β -sheets. In addition, position 562 is marked. The lipid-binding pocket extends on both sides of position 562(4). Thus, lipid binding of dynamin 2 seems to be of great importance to normal platelet function.

Experimental Approach

Experimental Model

Megakaryocyte lineage specific conditional *DNM2* knockout mice were used as an experimental model, allowing the study of the relationship between Charcot-Marie Tooth disease mutants and thrombocytopenia in greater detail. Crossing *DNM2^{loxP}* mice with *Pf4-Cre* mice generated conditional knockout mice in the megakaryocyte lineage (33). The knockout mice have a characteristic phenotype, in that they suffer from severe thrombocytopenia with macrothrombocytes, splenomegaly and massive megakaryocyte hyperplasia in spleen and bone marrow. Functionally, the mice suffer from a platelet deficiency as revealed by prolonged bleeding time (unpublished data, Falet, H.).

Parameter	<i>Dnm2^{loxP}</i>	<i>Dnm2^{loxP} Pf4-Cre</i>	
Platelets (K/ μ l)	816 \pm 82	274 \pm 123	-66%
MPV (fl)	4.78 \pm 0.24	7.28 \pm 0.50	+52%
Bleeding time (s)	98	>600	
Spleen (mg/g)	3.43 \pm 0.49	15.08 \pm 1.29	x4.4
Spleen MKs/field	2.7 \pm 0.3	145.6 \pm 4.2	x54
BM MKs/field	19.4 \pm 1.2	76.2 \pm 3.0	x3.9

Table 1 Phenotypes of *DNM2^{loxP}* and *DNM2^{loxP} PF4-Cre* mice, MPV: mean platelet volume, MK: megakaryocyte, BM: bone marrow (unpublished data Falet, H.)

Hypothesis

The phenotype of the experimental model signifies two inadequacies regarding platelets. One is an imbalance between sufficient platelet production and clearance and one is a functional defect. Possibly, the bleeding disorder results from thrombocytopenia *and* malfunctioning platelets. Thus, dynamin may be involved in the production and function of platelets.

Aside from combined disorders, thrombocytopenia can be categorized into three, namely (i) production disorders (ii) disorders of distribution and (iii) disorders of destruction(22). Letting functional aspects of dynamin guide the hypothesis, the current hypothesis proposes that the phenotype is rooted in a production disorder. Dynamin functions involve membrane scission(21). The hypothesis proposes that dynamin 2 is involved in thrombopoiesis by fragmentation of pro-platelets thereby giving rise to circulating platelets. In the absence of dynamin 2, it seems that no sufficient alternative cleavage pathway exists resulting in fewer and bigger platelets. The increase in size indicates that the megakaryocytes give rise to platelets, but in a less efficient manner, in the sense that (i) the cleavage process evolves less smoothly and (ii) the products have functional defects. Increase in platelet size suggests the former. Prolonged bleeding time suggests the latter. Together, the two manifestations indicate that in mice, dynamin 2 is involved in thrombopoiesis and normal physiological properties of platelets. Possibly, splenomegaly and megakaryocyte hyperplasia reflect a compensation mechanism, where the absence of functional platelets induces megakaryopoiesis. Due to failed thrombopoiesis; the consequence of megakaryopoiesis is megakaryocyte hyperplasia. In sum, the hypothesis states that the knockout mice suffer from a platelet development deficiency and proposes that dynamin 2 facilitates the fragmentation of platelets. Further, it argues that dynamin 2 is involved in normal functional properties of platelets.

The hypothesis may as well be transferred to thrombocytopenia in Charcot-Marie Tooth disease patients. The fact that the effect of the K562 mutations is interference with lipid binding(4) makes it likely, that dynamin 2 is involved in the fragmentation of platelets, in that membrane scission results from lipid binding. Thus, a joint investigation is justified given that the same mechanisms guide thrombocytopenia in Charcot-Marie Tooth disease patients and in the knockout mice.

Experimental Object

The methodological aim is to localize the protein construct comprised of dynamin 2 and Dendra2. Potentially, this method will enable studying the location and *dynamics* of dynamin 2 during thrombopoiesis *in vitro*. Currently no antibody against dynamin 2 exists. Therefore, the methodological aim is a central aspect of the experiments presented in this thesis. Upon successful localization, the object is to investigate if:

Induction of wild type dynamin 2 in knockout megakaryocytes will rescue platelets deficiency.

Confirmation of the object will demonstrate that dynamin 2 associated thrombocytopenia is reversible.

Oppositely, rejection of the object will leave the question of the functional role of dynamin 2 in thrombopoiesis unresolved.

Materials and Methods

Plasmid Construct

The experiments were carried out using the plasmid construct shown in figure 8. It is comprised of a pMSCVneo vector backbone, Dendra2 and the dynamin 2 sequence. The vector backbone carries an ampicillin resistance gene and the viral packaging signal Ψ^+ . The ampicillin resistance gene was used as a selection marker and Ψ^+ is required for retroviral production. Further, the vector carries a long term repeat that allows the gene of interest to be expressed in hematopoietic and embryonic stem cells.

Figure 8 illustrates the mutation site, which is a cysteine insert that derives from a construction error.

Figure 8 Plasmid construct with mutation site; DNM2: dynamin 2, MSCV: Murine Stem Cell Virus

Mutagenesis

Cysteine insert was obtained using the *Dendra2-DNM2-MSCV-vector*, kindly provided by Markus Bender and *QuickChange II XL Site-Generated Mutagenesis Kit* (Agilent Technologies, Cat. no 2005521). The procedure contains three steps as illustrated in figure 9. First, a site directed

mutation was introduced via polymerase chain reaction using the *Dendra2-DNM2-MSCV-vector* as template at 1 ng/μL and the primers carrying the desired mutation at 300 nM. The primer sequences are listed in table 5. Second, template plasmids were digested with the Dpn I endonuclease, that cuts methylated and hemimethylated DNA. Hence it digests the template plasmid, but not the polymerase chain reaction product. To yield circular plasmids, the digestion product was transformed into *XL-10 ultracompetent cells* and grown in Super Optimal Broth Medium with Catabolite repression. Transformation products were grown overnight on agar plates with ampicillin at 100μg/mL.

Figure 9 Mutagenesis adapted from QuikChange II XL Site-Directed Mutagenesis Kit, Instruction Manual Catalog #200521: I.: Mutagenesis, II.: Digestion, III.: Transformation

Primer	Sequence
Forward	5'-CAAGACCTCGAGCATGGGCAACCGCGGGA-3'
Reverse	5'-TCCCGCGGTTGCCCATGCTCGAGGTCTCTTG-3'

Table 2 Primers (Invitrogen) used for mutagenesis

DNA Purification

Colonies were cultured overnight in 3 mL L-Broth medium with ampicillin at 50 μg/mL. Plasmids were purified using the *QIAprep Spin Miniprep Kit (250)* (Qiagen, Cat. No. 27106). Positive cultures were identified from test digestions. These were grown on agar plates overnight. Then, colonies were picked and cultured overnight in 100 mL L-Broth medium with ampicillin and purified with the *HiSpeed Plasmid Midi Kit* (Qiagen Cat. No. 12643). Plasmids were eluted in UltraPure H₂O. Finally, the DNA concentration was measured using *NanoDrop 1000 Spectrophotometer* (ThermoScientific) and sent for sequencing.

Retroviral Production

The retroviral production was carried out using HEK 293T cells as packaging cells and the pCL helper plasmid. The steps involved in the process are presented in figure 9.

Figure 10 Retroviral production: I.: Co-transfection, II.: Transcription, III.: Packaging, IV.: Budding off and harvest

The co-transfection was performed with the plasmid construct and the pCL helper plasmid that encodes the sequences for the packing proteins. The HEK 293T cells were grown in a 6-well plate to a confluency of 30-50 % in 2 mL of Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) (*Gibco 11885*) with 1% Penicillin/Streptococcus and 10% fetal-bovine-serum.

X-tremeGENE9 *Roche 06365787001* was diluted 3:50 in serum and incubated 5 minutes at room temperature. In each well 1 μ g of the plasmid construct and 1 μ g of the pCL helper plasmid were added and incubated at room temperature for 15 minutes. Then, 100 μ L of diluted X-tremeGENE9 was added to each well. Cells were incubated, media changed after 18 hours and supernatant harvested after 72 hours. Prior to storing at -80°C , supernatant was filtered using 0.45 μm , 25mm filters (*Fisher Scientific Ref. 097198*).

Megakaryocyte Treatment

Isolation

At day 0, fetal liver cells from mouse embryos aged 13.5-14.5 days were collected in DMEM with 10% fetal-bovine-serum and 1% Penicillin/Streptococcus. Tissue was saved for genotyping. Cells were passed with 1 mL pipet, 18G, 22G and 25G needles. Then, cells were transferred to a BD 40µm nylon moisten cell strainer (*BD Ref. 352340*). Cells were spun at 200g for 5 minutes at room temperature and the pellets were resuspended in medium with 50ng/mL thrombopoietin and incubated at 37°C.

Transfection

At day 2, fetal liver cells were transfected. They were resuspended carefully, transferred to a 15 mL Falcon tube and spun at 200g for 5 minutes at room temperature. The pellets were resuspended in 1.5mL fresh DMEM. Then, 1 mL virus and 2.5µL polybrene were added to each well, transferred to a 6-well plate and spun (*Sorvall, RT6000B*) at 800g for 90 minutes at room temperature. Thereafter, the transfected cells were incubated for 90 minutes at 37°C. Then, cells were transferred to 15 mL Falcon tubes, spun at 200g for 5 minutes and resuspended in 2 mL DMEM with thrombopoietin and incubated overnight in a 6-well plate at 37°C. At day 3, megakaryocytes were resuspended in 1.5 mL fresh medium and isolated over a bovine-serum-albumin gradient at 1.5%/3.0% and cells were resuspended in fresh medium with thrombopoietin. At day 4, cells were visualized in a fluorescent-light-microscope and pictures were taken.

Methodological Achievements

I gained experience in molecular biological procedures from the experiments conducted. The molecular biological procedures count mutagenesis comprised of polymerase chain reaction and bacterial transformation, retroviral production and infection. Hence, I became familiar with two ways in which DNA multiplication may come about, one being polymerase chain reaction and one being bacterial growth. Finally, I became aware of the fact that retrovirus functions as a critical tool in manipulating cellular protein synthesis.

Results

Mutagenesis

Test digestions were performed to confirm successful transformation into the *XL-10* ultracompetent cells.

Figure 11 Test digestion with *Nco*I, left: 6 samples and 2 negative controls on 0.8% agarose gel at 120V for 30 minutes, right: expected band pattern

Figure 11 demonstrates that digestion of the purified plasmid yields a band corresponding to the expected band size. Furthermore, digestion with the restriction enzyme *Bgl*III that has three cleavage sites on the plasmid yielded the expected band pattern. A picture of the gel is shown in figure 12.

Figure 12 Test digestion with *Bgl*III, left: 6 samples and 2 negative controls on 0.8% agarose gel at 120V for 30 minutes, right: expected band pattern

To confirm successful mutation, two samples were sent for sequencing. Results are presented in figure 13.

Figure 13 Sequencing results: From left: sequence prior to cysteine insert, 2 samples after successful cysteine insert. The arrows mark site of interest.

Retroviral Production

Pictures were taken 48 hours after transfection to confirm successful transfection of the HEK 293T cells. The pictures provide a qualitative estimate of the transfection efficiency and they demonstrate that the distribution of dynamin 2 is confined to the cytoplasm as expected.

Figure 14 HEK 293T cells, 4X bright field and fluorescence, 48 hours after transfection

The estimate of the transfection efficiency does not transfer to information on the retroviral production, explicitly. Hence, neither the quality nor the quantity of the virus was determined.

Megakaryocyte Transfection

Pictures of the transfected megakaryocytes are shown in figure 15, 16 and 17. The size of the cells is used to identify the megakaryocytes. The megakaryocyte diameter in mice ranges from 20-30 μm (34).

Figure 15 Transfected wild type megakaryocyte, bright field and fluorescence, 48 hours after transfection

Figure 16 Transfected knockout megakaryocytes, bright field and fluorescence, 48 hours after transfection

Figure 17 Transfection trend in knockout megakaryocytes, bright field fluorescence and fluorescence, 48 hours after transfection

Discussion

Descriptive Summary

Figure 15 and 16 reveal that the transfection is successful in wild type and knockout cells. However, the transfection efficiency is low, reducing the informative potential of the pictures. Furthermore, no pro-platelet formation occurs. Based on the experimental model that shows decreased platelet count in knockout mice, sparse formation of pro-platelets is to be expected. The distribution of dynamin 2 is more scattered in megakaryocytes than in HEK 293T cells. Yet, a clear pattern in the location of dynamin 2 cannot be deduced from the pictures. The combination of relatively low transfection efficiency and the apparent lack of specific location of dynamin 2 prohibits any conclusions to be drawn whether rescuing of the knockout megakaryocyte has been obtained.

A comparison between the wild type and knockout megakaryocytes (figure 15 and 16 bright field pictures), shows that the wild type cells are more numerous and bigger, suggesting a difference between the behavior of megakaryocytes *in vivo* and *in vitro*, since the experimental model is characterized by megakaryocyte hyperplasia. Either, the pictures are not representative, or the megakaryocyte progenitors respond differently to thrombopoietin *in vivo* and *in vitro*. The response to thrombopoietin *in vivo* may be integrated with other stimuli, allowing the megakaryocytes to proliferate in the absence of dynamin 2. Alternatively, it can be hypothesized that megakaryocyte proliferation in dynamin 2 knockout mice accelerates postpartum or later in the embryonic development. Accordingly, megakaryocyte hyperplasia does not present in cultures from embryos.

Figure 17 illustrates the trend of the transfected cells, which can be categorized in to three, namely: untransfected cells, resting transfected cells and active transfected cells. The terms *resting* and *active* are coupled to the appearance of the cell membrane *active* cells meaning cells where the cell membrane appears disrupted.

As opposed to figure 15 and 16, figure 17 indirectly pictures the multi lobular nucleus of the megakaryocytes, making the identification of the cell more reliable. Antibody staining against lineage specific surface molecules in the megakaryocyte lineage is required to confirm the nature of the cells.

It seems that there is a difference between the location of dynamin 2 in active and resting cells, in that the location of dynamin 2 in active cells is limited to specific areas in close proximity to the cell membrane. Additionally, the fluorescence is stronger in the resting cells than in the active cells, suggesting that the expression of dynamin 2 varies depending on the functional identity of the cells.

In summary, the quality of the pictures is not good enough to allow conclusions to be drawn. First, the combination of low transfection efficiency and no pro-platelet formation hinders visualization of transfected pro-platelets. Second, the unspecific localization of dynamin 2 in transfected cells does not point to any clear relation between thrombopoiesis and function of dynamin 2.

Experimental Evaluation

Other than the low transfection efficiency, it is a major problem that no pro-platelets are seen in the pictures. Since there are no substantial differences between pro-platelets formation of wild type and knockout megakaryocytes, absence of pro-platelets is most likely a consequence of the experimental circumstances. The lack of pro-platelet formation may result from (i) the viral transfection or (ii) the Dendra2-intervention. In case of (i) the viral transfection, including centrifugation may be too harsh on the cells. As a result, the cells may be more susceptible to apoptosis. Further investigation of this possibility requires identification of apoptotic bodies. In line with that, it should be noted, that the concentration of the viral supernatant used for transfection is not adjusted. The element gives rise to two problems. First, the cell cultures are not necessarily treated alike. Second, the amount of viral supernatant used for transfection may be either too little or too much to obtain sufficient expression levels.

In case of the subtler (ii), the experimental setup assumes that Dendra2 does not disrupt the functional integrity of dynamin 2. To date, successful labeling of other polymerizing proteins have been reported, among them another nucleotide hydrolyzing protein, namely tubulin (35). Assuming that dynamin 2 orchestrates platelet fragmentation, sparse pro-platelet formation may result in a drop in the functional integrity of dynamin 2 in transfected cells, caused by Dendra2. Based on that, the properties of dynamin 2 and Dendra2-dynamin 2 ought to be studied separately to ensure reliable data.

Experimental Limits

From the experimental model and the Charcot-Marie Tooth disease patients, it seems that dynamin 2 is a protein of great importance in mice and humans. Nevertheless the patients and the experimental model differ, and the differences are critical to keep in mind in the attempt to map thrombocytopenia in Charcot-Marie Tooth disease patients and the mouse model.

For example, the Charcot-Marie Tooth disease patients do express dynamin 2, although the function is altered due to mutations. In contrast, the knockout of dynamin 2 in the experimental model is lineage specific. Hence, the patients and the model differ fundamentally, aside from differences resulting from the fact that they are different animals. Possibly, genetic redundancy may preserve some functions of dynamin 2 in the Charcot-Marie Tooth disease patients. That possibility may explain why thrombocytopenia in Charcot-Marie Tooth disease

patients is limited to one mutation site. In addition, the presence of dynamin 2 in the patients, albeit mutated, may sustain some dynamin 2 functions.

Conclusion

Experimentally, the site-directed mutagenesis yielded positive results, whereas the attempt to locate dynamin 2 with Dendra2 was inconclusive because of low transfection efficiency combined with sparse pro-platelet formation. Hence, the experiments gave no basis to confirm or reject the hypothesis, namely that dynamin 2 facilitates the fragmentation of platelets from pro-platelets.

While acknowledging the fact that the experiments were conducted with limited expertise and time, the thesis evaluates the experimental setup and draws attention to certain features of the experiments. Specifically, the evaluation raises two main questions regarding the experimental procedures, (i) that they may be too harsh on the megakaryocytes and (ii) that Dendra2 may interrupt the functional integrity of dynamin 2.

Personally, the work gave me insight in to central molecular biological experimental procedures that have a broad application in research and clinically. Additionally, I studied platelet development and function and dynamin structure and function. Thereby I learned to acquire knowledge from scientific articles and communicate these insights in writing.

References

1. Thon JN, Italiano JE. Platelets: production, morphology and ultrastructure. Handbook of experimental pharmacology. 2012(210):3-22.
2. Ribatti D, Crivellato E. Giulio Bizzozzero and the discovery of platelets. Leukemia research. 2007;31(10):1339-41.
3. Becker RC, Smyth S. The evolution of platelet-directed pharmacotherapy. Journal of thrombosis and haemostasis : JTH. 2009;7 Suppl 1:266-71.
4. Zuchner S, Nouredine M, Kennerson M, Verhoeven K, Claeys K, De Jonghe P, et al. Mutations in the pleckstrin homology domain of dynamin 2 cause dominant intermediate Charcot-Marie-Tooth disease. Nature genetics. 2005;37(3):289-94.
5. Ferguson SM, De Camilli P. Dynamin, a membrane-remodelling GTPase. Nature reviews Molecular cell biology. 2012;13(2):75-88.
6. Chudakov DM, Lukyanov S, Lukyanov KA. Using photoactivatable fluorescent protein Dendra2 to track protein movement. BioTechniques. 2007;42(5):553, 5, 7 passim.
7. Gurskaya NG, Verkhusha VV, Shcheglov AS, Staroverov DB, Chepurnykh TV, Fradkov AF, et al. Engineering of a monomeric green-to-red photoactivatable fluorescent protein induced by blue light. Nature biotechnology. 2006;24(4):461-5.
8. Shpetner Hs Fau - Vallee RB, Vallee RB. Identification of dynamin, a novel mechanochemical enzyme that mediates interactions between microtubules. (0092-8674 (Print)).
9. Robinson PJ, Sontag JM, Liu JP, Fykse EM, Slaughter C, McMahon H, et al. Dynamin GTPase regulated by protein kinase C phosphorylation in nerve terminals. Nature. 1993;365(6442):163-6.
10. Sontag JM, Fykse EM, Ushkaryov Y, Liu JP, Robinson PJ, Sudhof TC. Differential expression and regulation of multiple dynamins. The Journal of biological chemistry. 1994;269(6):4547-54.
11. Cook TA, Urrutia R, McNiven MA. Identification of dynamin 2, an isoform ubiquitously expressed in rat tissues. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America. 1994;91(2):644-8.
12. Nakata T, Takemura R, Hirokawa N. A novel member of the dynamin family of GTP-binding proteins is expressed specifically in the testis. Journal of cell science. 1993;105 (Pt 1):1-5.
13. Zhang P, Hinshaw JE. Three-dimensional reconstruction of dynamin in the constricted state. Nature cell biology. 2001;3(10):922-6.
14. Gout I, Dhand R, Hiles ID, Fry MJ, Panayotou G, Das P, et al. The GTPase dynamin binds to and is activated by a subset of SH3 domains. Cell. 1993;75(1):25-36.
15. Salim K, Bottomley MJ, Querfurth E, Zvelebil MJ, Gout I, Scaife R, et al. Distinct specificity in the recognition of phosphoinositides by the pleckstrin homology domains of dynamin and Bruton's tyrosine kinase. The EMBO journal. 1996;15(22):6241-50.
16. Chen YJ, Zhang P, Egelman EH, Hinshaw JE. The stalk region of dynamin drives the constriction of dynamin tubes. Nature structural & molecular biology. 2004;11(6):574-5.
17. Wunderlich L, Farago A, Buday L. Characterization of interactions of Nck with Sos and dynamin. Cellular signalling. 1999;11(1):25-9.
18. Shajahan AN, Timblin BK, Sandoval R, Tiruppathi C, Malik AB, Minshall RD. Role of Src-induced dynamin-2 phosphorylation in caveolae-mediated endocytosis in endothelial cells. The Journal of biological chemistry. 2004;279(19):20392-400.
19. Mears JA, Ray P, Hinshaw JE. A corkscrew model for dynamin constriction. Structure (London, England : 1993). 2007;15(10):1190-202.
20. Roux A, Uyhazi K, Frost A, De Camilli P. GTP-dependent twisting of dynamin implicates constriction and tension in membrane fission. Nature. 2006;441(7092):528-31.
21. Morlot S, Roux A. Mechanics of dynamin-mediated membrane fission. Annual review of biophysics. 2013;42:629-49.

22. Harker LA, Finch CA. Thrombokinetics in man. *The Journal of clinical investigation*. 1969;48(6):963-74.
23. Wright JH. The histogenesis of the blood platelets. *Journal of Morphology*. 1910;21(2):263-78.
24. Italiano JE, Jr., Lecine P, Shivdasani RA, Hartwig JH. Blood platelets are assembled principally at the ends of proplatelet processes produced by differentiated megakaryocytes. *The Journal of cell biology*. 1999;147(6):1299-312.
25. Radley JM, Scurfield G. The mechanism of platelet release. *Blood*. 1980;56(6):996-9.
26. Rabellino EM, Nachman RL, Williams N, Winchester RJ, Ross GD. Human megakaryocytes. I. Characterization of the membrane and cytoplasmic components of isolated marrow megakaryocytes. *The Journal of experimental medicine*. 1979;149(6):1273-87.
27. Ruggeri ZM, Dent JA, Saldivar E. Contribution of distinct adhesive interactions to platelet aggregation in flowing blood. *Blood*. 1999;94(1):172-8.
28. Ebbe S, Stohlman F, Jr. MEGAKARYOCYTOPOIESIS IN THE RAT. *Blood*. 1965;26:20-35.
29. Kosaki G. Platelet production by megakaryocytes: protoplatelet theory justifies cytoplasmic fragmentation model. *International journal of hematology*. 2008;88(3):255-67.
30. Harrison P, Martin Cramer E. Platelet α -granules. *Blood reviews*. 1993;7(1):52-62.
31. Bitoun M, Bevilacqua JA, Eymard B, Prudhon B, Fardeau M, Guicheney P, et al. A new centronuclear myopathy phenotype due to a novel dynamin 2 mutation. *Neurology*. 2009;72(1):93-5.
32. . Available from: <http://zhanglab.ccmb.med.umich.edu/I-TASSER/>.
33. Nurnberg ST, Rendon A, Smethurst PA, Paul DS, Voss K, Thon JN, et al. A GWAS sequence variant for platelet volume marks an alternative DNMT3 promoter in megakaryocytes near a MEIS1 binding site. *Blood*. 2012;120(24):4859-68.
34. Schmitt A Fau - Guichard J, Guichard J Fau - Masse JM, Masse Jm Fau - Debili N, Debili N Fau - Cramer EM, Cramer EM. Of mice and men: comparison of the ultrastructure of megakaryocytes and platelets. (0301-472X (Print)).
35. Dovas A, Gligorijevic B, Chen X, Entenberg D, Condeelis J, Cox D. Visualization of actin polymerization in invasive structures of macrophages and carcinoma cells using photoconvertible beta-actin-Dendra2 fusion proteins. *PloS one*. 2011;6(2):e16485.